

ORGANO-ARSENICALS. PART I. SOME NEW N-ISOCYCLIC AMIDOSULPHOPHENYLARSONIC ACIDS*

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Fifteen N-isocyclic amidosulphophenyl-4'-arsonic acids have been synthesised by the application of Bart's reaction to each of the three isomeric OH-, OMe-, NO₂, CH₃- and COOH- substituted N¹-phenylsulphanilamides. The three N-nitrophenylamidosulphophenyl-4'-arsonic acids have been reduced to the [corresponding aminoarsonic acids. N¹-*o*- and N¹-*m*-methoxyphenylsulphanilamides have been described.

The most satisfactory general method for the synthesis of aryl arsonic acids is by the application of Bart's reaction (D. R. P. 250264), where the diazo group is replaced by the AsO(OH)₂- group in accordance with the following equation :

In the present investigation, eighteen N-isocyclic amidosulphophenyl-4'-arsonic acids of type (I) (vide Table I) have been synthesised, the first fifteen were prepared by the application of Bart's reaction to the appropriate N¹-isocyclic sulphanilamides and the remaining three (16, 17, 18) by the reduction of the corresponding nitro derivatives (7, 8, 9) with ferrous sulphate and alkali.

TABLE I

*Eighteen N-R''-sulphophenyl-4'-arsonic acids of type (I) where
R''-stands for:*

(1) 2-Hydroxyphenylamido-	(10) 2-Methylphenylamido-
(2) 3- " " "	(11) 3- " " "
(3) 4- " " "	(12) 4- " " "
(4) 2-Methoxyphenylamido-	(13) 2-Carboxyphenylamido-
(5) 3- " " "	(14) 3- " " "
(6) 4- " " "	(15) 4- " " "
(7) 2-Nitrophenylamido-	(16) 2-Aminophenylamido-
(8) 3- " " "	(17) 3- " " "
(9) 4- " " "	(18) 4- " " "

* A note on this work was published in *Science & Culture*, 1945-46, 11, 566.

Webster and Powers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 1553) prepared N¹-*o*-, *m*-, and *p*-hydroxyphenylsulphanilamides of type (II) by condensing *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonylchloride with the respective aminophenols and hydrolysing the resulting N¹-hydroxyphenyl-N⁴-acetylsulphanilamides of type (III) where R stands for -OH.

Northey (*Chem. Rev.*, 1940, 27, 97) has mentioned N¹-*o*-methoxyphenylsulphanilamide but details of its preparation have not been available. Therefore this compound (II, R = *o*-OMe) and its *meta*-isomer, which is described for the first time, have now been prepared by reacting *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonyl chloride with *o*- and *m*-anisidines respectively and hydrolysing the acetyl derivatives thus obtained. Choudhury, Das-Gupta and Basu (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 733) prepared the *p*-isomer in a similar manner using *p*-anisidine.

N¹-*o*-, *m*- & *p*-Nitrophenylsulphanilamides have been prepared before (Webster and Powers, *loc. cit.* Bauer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 613).

The three N¹-methyl and N¹-carboxyphenylsulphanilamides were prepared according to known methods (*cf.* Northey, *loc. cit.* Gelmo, *J. parkl. Chem.*, 1908, *ii.* 77, 369; Kolloff, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 950; Bauer, *ibid.*, 1939, 61, 613).

According to French Patent No. 624028 N¹-2-carboxyphenylamidodisulphophenyl-4'-arsonic acid (No 13 of Table I) was prepared in 37% yield by the application of Scheller's reaction on N¹-*o*-carboxyphenylsulphanilamide using AsCl₃ and a catalyst like CuCl. Oneto and Way (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 762) prepared this compound in 54% yield by condensing *p*-chlorosulphophenylarsonic acid with *o*-aminobenzoic acid. By the application of the Bart's reaction it has now been prepared in 50% yield.

The arsonic acids described here have no definite melting points. They are soluble in alkalis and carbonates but insoluble in common organic solvents and mineral acids.

N-2-Hydroxyphenylamidodisulphophenyl-4'-arsonic acid, (1).—*N*¹-*o*-Hydroxyphenylsulphanilamide (13.2 g.), dissolved in 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid (33 c.c.), was diazotised with sodium nitrite (3.5 g.) in water (80 c.c.). The resulting diazonium solution was poured under cooling and stirring into a solution of sodium arsenite (9.6 g.) in water (100 c.c.) containing sodium hydroxide (10 g.) and heated on a water-bath till the evolution of nitrogen ceased. The liquid was then cooled and acidified with hydrochloric acid when the arsonic acid separated. It was filtered, washed with water and purified by dissolution in sodium carbonate solution and precipitation with acid, yield 7.5 g.

Compounds (16), (17) and (18) were obtained on reducing compound (7), (8) and (9) respectively with ferrous sulphate and alkali according to details given for compound (16) below.

N-2-Aminophenylamidodisulphophenyl-4'-arsonic Acid, (16).—Sodium hydroxide solution (10% 110 c.c.) was added in small quantities at a time to an ice-cold solution of ferrous sulphate (30 g.) in water (75 c.c.) under stirring when the ferrous hydroxide separated in the form of a green mud. Compound No. 7 (6 g.), dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (10% 40 c.c.) was poured into the ferrous hydroxide mixture and shaken thoroughly during 15 minutes when the colour of the mud changed from green to brown indicating its conversion into ferric hydroxide. The mud was then filtered out and washed with water. When the combined filtrates were acidified with acetic acid, the product separated and was collected, washed and purified, yield 3 g.

*N*¹-*o*-Methoxyphenyl-*N*⁴-acetylulphanilamide, (III, R = *o*-OMe).—To freshly distilled *o*-anisidine (10 g.), crude air-dried *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonylchloride (10 g.) was gradually added with stirring. The mixture was then heated on a water-bath for half an hour and the mass, thus obtained, was ground with 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid when the product separated out. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 204-205°, yield 11 g.

The yield improved when the condensation was carried out in presence of sodium acetate. To a suspension of *o*-anisidine (5 g.) in hot (75°) water (100 c.c.) containing anhydrous sodium acetate (3 g.), *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonylchloride (10 g.) was gradually added with stirring. After half an hour the product separating was filtered, washed with water and crystallised as before, yield 12 g. (Found : C, 56.01 ; H, 4.95. C₁₅H₁₄O₄N₂S requires C, 56.26 ; H, 5.00 per cent).

*N*¹-*o*-Methoxyphenylsulphanilamide, (II, R = *o*-OMe).—The above acetamino compound (12 g.) was refluxed with 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid (25 c.c.) till all the solid went into solution. The hydrochloride of the amine, which separated out on cooling, was collected, redissolved in minimum quantity of water and the solution basified with ammonia when the product precipitated out. This was filtered, washed, and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 186°, yield 10.3 g. (Found : C, 55.93 ; H, 5.00. C₁₃H₁₄O₃N₂S requires C, 56.11 ; H, 5.04 per cent).

*N*¹-*m*-Methoxyphenyl-*N*⁴-acetylsulphanilamide, (III, R = *m*-OMe).—To a suspension of *m*-anisidine (3 g.) in hot water (100 c c) containing anhydrous sodium acetate (2 g.), *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonylchloride (6 g.) was gradually added under stirring. After half an hour, the product which had separated was collected and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 177-78°, yield 6 g. (Found : C, 55.98 ; H, 4.91. C₁₅H₁₆O₄N₂S requires C, 56.26 ; H, 5.00 per cent):

*N*¹-*m*-Methoxyphenylsulphanilamide (II, R = *m*-OMe).—The above acetamino compound (12 g.) was hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid and the product isolated in the usual manner, m. p. 150° yield 10.4 g. (Found : C, 55.90 ; H, 4.98. C₁₅H₁₄O₃N₂S requires C, 56.11 ; H, 5.04 per cent).

The analytical data for the eighteen arsonic acids are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Compound No.	Formula.	% Arsenic		Compound No.	Formula.	% Arsenic	
		Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
1.	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₄ NSAs	19.99	20.11	10.	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₄ NSAs	20.13	20.21
2.	"	19.84	20.11	11.	"	20.18	20.21
3.	"	19.87	20.11	12.	"	20.12	20.21
4.	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃ NSAs	19.23	19.32	13.	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₇ NSAs	18.79	18.71
5.	"	19.30	19.33	14.	"	18.81	18.71
6.	"	19.17	19.35	15.	"	18.92	18.71
7.	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₇ N ₂ SAAs	18.51	18.66	16.	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ SAAs	19.98	20.17
8.	"	18.49	18.66	17.	"	20.01	20.17
9.	"	18.41	18.66	18.	"	19.87	20.17

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Received December 6, 1947.